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BACHELOR'S THESIS

Graph embeddings for blockchain-induced
networks

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	The world of Ethereum	2
2.1	What is the Ethereum blockchain?	2
2.2	Interactions on the Ethereum network	3
2.3	Accounts	4
2.4	Transactions	4
3	Graph level embedding	5
3.1	Spectral features	5
3.2	Family of graph spectral distances	6
3.3	Graph2Vec	7
4	Dimensionality reduction	10
4.1	Why reduce dimensions?	10
4.1.1	The curse of dimensionality	10
4.2	How to reduce dimensions?	11
4.2.1	Feature selection	11
4.2.2	Principal Component Analysis	12
4.2.3	The steps of PCA	14
5	Ethereum dataset	16
5.1	Stablecoins	16
5.2	Data collection	17
5.2.1	Banned users	17
5.2.2	Collecting the neighborhood	18
6	Experiments	20
6.1	Graph classification	20
6.1.1	Evaluation Metrics	20
6.1.2	Classification models	22
6.1.3	Results	23
6.2	Embedding visualization	30
7	Summary	34
	Appendix	38

1 Introduction

In recent years, the rapid growth of blockchain technology has sparked massive curiosity and transformed various industries. Among the numerous blockchain platforms, Ethereum has gathered significant attention for its decentralized applications and smart contracts. Understanding Ethereum and its network interactions is a challenging task but with various methods at our disposal, such as graph embeddings, we gain valuable insight into its operations.

Graph embeddings are powerful techniques in the realm of data representation which have become a focal point in analyzing complex structures. By capturing the essence of graph's structure and semantics, embeddings enable efficient analysis of vast networks. In the context of blockchain-induced networks, graph embeddings offer effective insights into the behavior and dynamics of transactions and addresses.

In my Bachelor's thesis, conducted under the guidance and support of Dr. Ferenc Béres and Marcell Nagy, I aim to explore the connection between graph embeddings and blockchain-induced networks from Ethereum with a binary classification problem on certain Ethereum accounts' network interactions as graphs. Additionally, I analyze graph-level properties and employ dimensionality reduction techniques to visualize these networks in the embedding space.

My thesis is structured as follows:

- The fundamental concepts of the Ethereum blockchain and its key features are introduced in Chapter 2.
- Chapter 3 is dedicated to different methods of graph embeddings and their significance in network analysis.
- The importance of dimensionality reduction and Principal Component Analysis are assessed in Chapter 4.
- In Chapter 5, I describe the data collection process and how networks were built from raw data for my experiments.
- Next, I present our binary classification results for Ethereum transaction graphs in Chapter 6.
- Finally, I conclude my thesis with a short summary in Chapter 7.

Without any further ado, let me start the journey of exploring the captivating realm where graph embeddings and blockchain-induced networks intersect.

2 The world of Ethereum

To fully understand my work, we must look at where the data originates. I have always been interested in the rise of cryptocurrencies in recent years. Still, until now, I did not look into the background processes and the necessary basis of these networks. In my bachelor thesis, I study Ethereum, a cryptocurrency network that has captured my interest. In this chapter, I introduce the Ethereum network and highlight some of its key features. For a more detailed description, I recommend the reader to follow Ethereum developers' documentation¹. I start with explaining the notion of a blockchain.

2.1 What is the Ethereum blockchain?

A *blockchain* is a public database that is updated and shared across a network of computers. It is made up of two very important words, "Block" and "Chain". The first refers to data and states being stored together in sequential order. For example, each transaction where you send *Ether* (*ETH*) - the native currency in Ethereum - to someone, it must be included in this fundamental unit, called *blocks* on the related Ethereum blockchain, see Figure 1. The latter word refers to the fact that blocks get chained together in a way where each block references its parent. This is beneficial because the data in a block cannot change without changing all the blocks after it, which would require the consensus of the whole network. These references to the previous block help maintain the order over all blocks.

The network consists of several computers known as *nodes*. In our case, each *node* runs the Ethereum client software while it is connected to other computers also running this software. The client software ensures that everyone has the same data and uses the same protocols to validate and verify every new block. Thus, keeping the network secure is a community effort. Ethereum uses a so-called proof-of-stake consensus mechanism which means that before a node adds a new block, the node has to stake *ETH* as collateral and run validator software. There is a reward and penalty system that encourages people to propose only valid blocks and to be online with their nodes as much as possible.

Ethereum also has a built-in computer called the *Ethereum Virtual Machine*, or *EVM* for short. *EVM* is a canonical computer whose state is stored and maintained by the blockchain. Nodes can request the *EVM* to perform computations that are verified, validated, and carried out by other participants on the network. These requests are called transactions, and they cause state changes to the *EVM*. Again, new transactions get included in blocks that are verified and added to the blockchain.

¹<https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/>

An illustration of this process can be seen in Figure 1. Several cryptographic mechanisms ensure that verified data (blocks and transactions) cannot be changed later on, but this discussion goes beyond this thesis’s main focus.

Figure 1: Ethereum blocks filled with transactions changing the world state.

Source: <https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/blocks/>

2.2 Interactions on the Ethereum network

Anyone who makes a transaction request must offer an amount of *ETH* to the network as a transaction fee. This reward is claimed by whoever verifies the transaction, executes it, and commits it to the blockchain first. This amount is proportional to the resources required for the related computations.

Users do not write new code when they make requests to the *EVM*. Most of the time, they interact with services through smart contracts that are reusable snippets of code, uploaded to the *EVM* state by developers. A major advantage of smart contracts is that any developer can create them and make them public in exchange for a fee paid to the network. This way, any user can call them and execute their code, again for a fee paid. Various services can be built with smart contracts, such as exchanges, marketplaces, games, etc. Thus, smart contracts are often called decentralized apps (*dapps*).

Another great aspect of smart contracts is that they can be programmed in developer-friendly languages. There are languages with a syntax similar to Python, which is one of the most known programming languages in the world. On the Ethereum network, the two most frequently used languages are Solidity² and Vyper³.

²<https://soliditylang.org/>

³<https://docs.vyperlang.org/en/stable/>

2.3 Accounts

An *account* is an interface to interact with the Ethereum network. There are two types of accounts, *externally-owned accounts (EOA)* controlled by a human, and *contract accounts*, which are smart contracts deployed to the network. Both types are able to receive, send and hold *ETH* or other tokens and interact with other smart contracts. However, a major difference between them is that while EOAs are made up of a public and a private key, contract accounts are governed by code. They don't have any private keys. For EOAs, account owners sign transactions with their private key to ensure that a malicious adversary cannot initiate a transaction from their account. Private keys consist of 64 hexadecimal characters that can be encrypted with a password. The public key is derived from the account's private key using the *Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm*. The address for a given account is formed from the last 20 bytes of the public key's hash with an additional *0x* at the beginning.

2.4 Transactions

The most important element of the Ethereum network in connection with my thesis is *transactions*. From the previous sections we already know that transactions are orders from accounts that are cryptographically signed, and we also acknowledged that transactions change the state of the Ethereum network so it needs to be updated and accepted by all of the nodes except the one that requested it.

Transactions refer to an action started by a human-managed account. This action could be *ETH* transfers between two accounts to take the simplest example. Any node can broadcast this state-changing action to be executed and as mentioned before it has to be validated by the rest of the nodes on the *EVM*. If that happens, then the transaction results in an *EVM* state change. First, a transaction is placed in a block and when the block is full it gets validated. Only those transactions go through which are included in a validated block.

Let us look at the information that transactions carry. Transactions include the *from* field, which is the address of the signer who initiated the transaction. This address has to be a human-managed account address since that is the only account type that can begin transactions. The *recipient* field is the "to" field. This is the address that is receiving the value if it is an externally-owned account, or that is executing its code if it is a contract account. Transactions also include the *value* which is the amount of *ETH* to transfer.

3 Graph level embedding

In the field of machine learning, tabular data is usually the required input for algorithms such as Random Forest or Logistic Regression. However, when dealing with network data, it becomes advantageous to avoid feeding raw data in the form of graph adjacency or incidence matrices to downstream classifiers. With several techniques like kernel [26, 28, 29, 27], sequential [15, 37], and embedding [2, 11, 13, 25] approaches, graph representation learning has become a prominent area of research in machine learning. The learned low-dimensional representations can represent either individual nodes (node embedding) or entire graphs (whole-graph embedding). However, these methods often involve complex mathematics and computationally intensive operations. One major challenge is the graph isomorphism problem, which remains to be unsolved in polynomial time but can be mitigated by focusing on identifying similar or different structures rather than identical ones. This perspective change enables the creation of quicker and more efficient algorithms.

A previous study [3] focuses on the application of node embeddings to Ethereum data. Ethereum, being a decentralized blockchain platform, presents unique challenges in terms of analyzing graph structures and preserving privacy. In the context of Ethereum data analysis, node embeddings proved to be particularly useful. By representing Ethereum addresses as low-dimensional vectors, the authors were able to perform effective comparisons and identify patterns in the transaction graph. This enabled them to analyze the activities and behaviors of Ethereum users, assess the privacy guarantees of specific applications like coin mixers, and uncover potential vulnerabilities in the system.

In my work, I also focus on analyzing transaction graphs of Ethereum addresses. Inspired by the success of the previously mentioned study, I aim to use whole-graph embeddings instead of node embeddings for certain addresses introduced in Chapter 5. By representing entire graphs as low-dimensional vectors, I perform graph classification as a downstream task in Chapter 6.

3.1 Spectral features

The authors of [20] propose an algorithm based on the spectral decomposition of the normalized graph Laplacian for graph classification. The feature vectors derived from the graphs contain the spectral features of the graph. Hence this embedding method is called SF (Spectral Features).

The model utilizes the normalized Laplacian of G . To understand this, let me first introduce G . Let $G = (V, E)$ be an undirected, unweighted, and connected graph. If G is not connected, then the largest connected component is extracted. For every graph G , let $A \in \{0, 1\}^{|V| \times |V|}$ denote the boolean (unweighted) adjacency

matrix. Then, calculate $D = \text{diag}(A\mathbf{1})$, where $\mathbf{1}$ is a vector containing ones at each entry. Basically, D is the matrix of node degrees in the diagonal. The definition of the normalized Laplacian of G is the following:

$$\mathcal{L} = I - D^{-1/2}AD^{-1/2}$$

The inputs for the classifiers are going to be the k smallest positive eigenvalues, except for graphs with fewer than k nodes. For them, zero padding is applied to reach the required dimension k . Figure 2 depicts the major steps of SF. This representation is independent of node indexing because of the ordered spectrum representation. Also, it is quite convenient to use this approach since the eigenvalues of the normalized Laplacian fall between 0 and 2. Thus, no normalization or further preprocessing is needed before passing on these embedding vectors to standard classifiers. The eigenvalue 0 represents the number of connected components. Hence it is left out of the representation. Other eigenvalues indicate specific graph structures, such as eigenvalue 2, which denotes a bipartite structure.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the spectral features model. $\mathcal{L}$ denotes the Laplacian and $\hat{c}$ is the predicted class.

Source: [20]

The chosen classifier by the authors in [20] was the Random Forest Classifier (RFC) without parameter tuning. The model was evaluated against standard datasets from biology: MT, PTC, EZ, PF, NCI1 [16]. With RFC, the algorithm outperforms state-of-the-art algorithms while not relying on any node feature. It achieves the best performance on five out of the six datasets against algorithms such as Pyramid Match [27], Stochastic Graphlet Embedding [11], etc. This showed outstanding performance in graph classification tasks when [20] was published.

3.2 Family of graph spectral distances

The study [35] aims to find graph feature representations that possess uniqueness, stability, and sparsity. The title comes from the introduced *family of graph spectral*

distances (FGSD). Graph feature representations based on these distances with a simple SVM-based classification algorithm outperformed sophisticated state-of-the-art algorithms in classification at the time of publication without utilizing node label information.

The authors emphasize the importance of an explicit graph representation that is invariant under graph isomorphism but enables extracting useful graph features and capturing sub-structures. This representation is denoted as $\mathcal{R} : G \rightarrow (g_1, g_2, \dots, g_r)$ and from $\mathcal{R}$ we can derive a feature function $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_d)$ with which the classification problem is solved.

However, learning $\mathcal{R}$ has received limited attention in machine learning. The authors of [35] were inspired by a group theoretic approach included in the papers ([17, 18, 19]), which successfully applies the features to graph classification problems. Hence they focused on learning $\mathcal{R}$ and deriving $\mathcal{F}$ from it. Their approach is based on the assumption that the multiset of all pairwise node distances carries the graph’s atomic structure. This assumption is supported by the study of homometric structures [31], which are structures with the same multiset of interatomic distances on graphs. Non-homometric vertex sets have different multisets of distances. Also, empirical evidence found in [22] shows that the biharmonic distance multisets are unique for small connected graphs, further supporting the assumption.

This led the authors to discover the *Family of Graph Spectral Distances (FGSD)*. Their harmonic and biharmonic distances are suitable members for graph representation $\mathcal{R}$. For graph classification, where graphs can have different node sizes, the feature vector F is constructed from the histogram of $\mathcal{R}$ and fed into a standard classification algorithm.

The work specifically focuses on unlabeled graphs and demonstrates the superior performance of FGSD graph features compared to state-of-the-art algorithms. The evaluation was partly made on the same datasets from biology, previously mentioned in Section 3.1, and on five social network datasets.

3.3 Graph2Vec

The algorithm *graph2vec* [25] aims to learn representations of whole graphs by treating the graph as a document and the rooted subgraphs around each node as words that compose the document. It is designed to learn data-driven representations of arbitrary-sized graphs in an unsupervised manner, making it versatile for various graph analytics tasks like graph classification, clustering, and regression. Unlike graph kernels that rely on handcrafted features, *graph2vec*’s embeddings are learned from the data itself, eliminating the need for manual feature engineering. This approach is based on the concept behind *word2vec* [23], a modern word embedding

Figure 3: (a) doc2vec’s *skipgram* model and (b) graph2vec’s *skipgram* model
Source: [25]

algorithm, in which words that appear in similar contexts have similar meanings and, as a result, should have similar vector representations. An extension of this work exists for documents. *doc2vec* [21] aims to learn embeddings of word sequences.

During the learning process, *graph2vec* takes into account non-linear substructures in the form of rooted subgraphs, whereas some existing approaches, such as *sub2vec* [1], sample linear substructures like fixed-length random walks. As shown in Figure 3, *graph2vec* is basically an extension of *doc2vec* to network data, where graphs are treated as documents, and rooted subgraphs of a certain degree are viewed as words from a special language. The expectation from this extension is that structurally similar graphs will be close to each other in the embedding space, just like with documents. The graph embeddings learned by *graph2vec* can be used for various downstream graph analytics tasks, such as graph classification, as I also demonstrate in Chapter 6.

To fully understand this algorithm, let’s introduce some notations:

- Let $G = (N, E, \lambda)$ be a graph, where N represents a set of nodes, E is a set of edges, denoted as $E \subseteq (N \times N)$, and λ is a labeling function that assigns a unique label from the alphabet to each node $n \in N$. If λ exists, then G is considered labeled. Otherwise, it is considered unlabeled. In the case of unlabeled graphs, where no labeling function is provided, a procedure mentioned in a previous work [33] can be followed. This procedure suggests labeling the nodes with their degree, which refers to the number of edges incident to each node.
- Let $sg_n^d = (N_{sg}, E_{sg}, \lambda_{sg})$ be a subgraph in $G = (N, E, \lambda)$. More specifically, it is called a rooted subgraph of degree d around $n \in N$, which includes all nodes (and corresponding edges) within d steps from n .

As illustrated by Algorithm 1, *graph2vec* consists of two main steps: extracting rooted subgraphs and learning graph embeddings. For example, in each iteration ϵ , for each graph G_i :

Algorithm 1 GRAPH2VEC ($\mathbb{G}, D, \delta, \epsilon, \alpha$)

input: $\mathbb{G} = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$: Set of graphs such that each graph $G_i = (N_i, E_i, \lambda_i)$ for which embeddings have to be learnt
 D : Maximum degree of rooted subgraphs to be considered for learning embeddings. This will produce a vocabulary of subgraphs, $SG_{vocab} = \{sg_1, sg_2, \dots\}$ from all the graphs in $\mathbb{G}$
 δ : number of dimensions (embedding size)
 ϵ : number of epochs
 α : Learning rate

output: Matrix of vector representations of graphs $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathbb{G}| \times \delta}$

```
1: procedure GRAPH2VEC( $\mathbb{G}, D, \delta, \epsilon, \alpha$ )
2:   Initialization: Sample  $\Phi$  from  $\mathbb{R}^{|\mathbb{G}| \times \delta}$ 
3:   for  $e = 1$  to  $\epsilon$  do
4:      $\mathfrak{G} = \text{SHUFFLE}(\mathbb{G})$ 
5:     for each  $G_i \in \mathfrak{G}$  do
6:       for each  $n \in N_i$  do
7:         for  $d = 0$  to  $D$  do
8:            $sg_n^{(d)} := \text{GetWLSUBgraph}(n, G_i, d)$ 
9:            $J(\Phi) = -\log \text{Pr}(sg_n^{(d)} | \Phi(G))$ 
10:           $\Phi = \Phi - \alpha \frac{\partial J}{\partial \Phi}$ 
11:   return  $\Phi$ 
```

1. The Weisfeiler-Lehman (WL) relabeling strategy [33] is used for rooted subgraph sampling, which is also used by the WL kernel [36, 33]. In short, the algorithm recursively extracts subgraphs of increasing degrees around the root node, capturing higher-order and non-linear substructures for further information on extracting rooted subgraphs.
2. Then, *skipgram* model with negative sampling is employed to learn the embeddings of the graphs. The algorithm initializes the embeddings for all graphs in the dataset and iteratively refines them using stochastic gradient descent (SGD).

Finally, the evaluation in [25] demonstrated that graph2vec achieved high accuracy and efficiency in graph classification tasks, outperforming state-of-the-art substructure representation learning approaches and graph kernels in various benchmark datasets and additional real-world malware detection tasks.

4 Dimensionality reduction

The number of attributes, or features our data has, corresponds to the dimension of the data records. When it comes to data mining, it is crucial to have enough attributes to train a good model. Although, too many attributes can also be a problem. This is due to a lot of different factors, and one of the most common reasons is that in real life, attributes are not independent. Not every one of them carries new information. Thus, sometimes, the goal is to reduce the dimensions by finding the important attributes and transforming the attribute space into a smaller dimensional space while keeping the relevant structure of the data.

4.1 Why reduce dimensions?

There are several reasons why reducing the dimensionality of the data is beneficial, and we are going to go over a few of them.

Firstly, models are more likely to overfit on high-dimensional data, which means poor generalization for previously unseen data. This behavior can be explained by the curse of dimensionality which I am going to explain in the next subsection.

Furthermore, for many algorithms, the running time might also depend on the dimensions of the data, so it might take too much time to train the model for many attributes.

Dimensionality reduction might also help us understand the data. For example, it is best to visualize data points in a two or three-dimensional Euclidean space.

4.1.1 The curse of dimensionality

Numerous phenomena arise when it comes to analyzing high-dimensional data that do not occur in low-dimensional data. They appear in fields such as sampling, machine learning, data mining, and numerous others. In high dimensions, the concepts of “distance”, “angle”, and “volume” behave very unintuitively. Adding extra dimensions to the attribute space makes an exponential increase in the volume, so the same number of records with more attributes appear sparser than before. While the sparsity increases, the minimum distance in the data set grows. By this effect, the distance function is losing its expressiveness in high dimensions. Let us look at an example to illustrate this problem in a high-dimensional Euclidean space.

Imagine we have a hypersphere with a radius r and a hypercube with edges of length $2r$. We are in $\mathbb{R}^d$ which means there are d dimensions. Let us look at the volumes of these objects. The volume of the hypercube is $(2r)^d$. On the other hand, the volume of the hypersphere is $\frac{2r^d \pi^{d/2}}{d \Gamma(d/2)}$ from the following close form: $V_n(R) = \frac{\pi^{n/2}}{\Gamma(\frac{n}{2} + 1)} R^n$ where Γ is Euler’s gamma function. The gamma function

is the generalization of the factorial function to non-integer arguments. $\Gamma(s) := \int_0^\infty t^{s-1} e^{-t} dt$ and it also satisfies $\Gamma(n) = (n-1)!$ if n is a positive integer (so if $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$) and $\Gamma(n + \frac{1}{2}) = (n - \frac{1}{2})(n - \frac{3}{2}) \dots \frac{1}{2} \pi^{\frac{1}{2}}$ if n is a non-negative integer (so if $n \in \mathbb{N}$).

Now that we know $V_{\text{hypersphere}} = \frac{2r^d \pi^{d/2}}{d \Gamma(d/2)}$ and $V_{\text{hypercube}} = (2r)^d$ we can look at their ratio. In 2D the volume ratio is 0.79 , while in 3D the volume ratio is 0.52 . Let us divide $V_{\text{hypersphere}}$ with $V_{\text{hypercube}}$ to get that:

$$\frac{V_{\text{hypersphere}}}{V_{\text{hypercube}}} = \frac{\frac{2r^d \pi^{d/2}}{d \Gamma(d/2)}}{(2r)^d} = \frac{\pi^{d/2}}{d 2^{d-1} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } d \rightarrow \infty$$

We can also easily count the distance between the center and the corners for a given r , which is $r\sqrt{d}$. This increases without bound which means that if our data points are uniformly generated, then almost all points are near the boundary of the cube or sphere.

Further development of this is looking at a product distribution on points in $\mathbb{R}^d$ that is caused by a fixed distribution on real numbers. We have n random data points $P_1 \dots P_n$. The difference between the minimum and the maximum distance between our n data points and a randomly selected Q reference point converges to 0 as we approach infinite dimensions for any given n . In other words:

$$\lim_{d \rightarrow \infty} E \left(\frac{\text{dist}_{\max}(d) - \text{dist}_{\min}(d)}{\text{dist}_{\min}(d)} \right) \rightarrow 0.$$

As a consequence, high-dimensional, uniformly distributed data set data points are far away from each other and also from the origin.

4.2 How to reduce dimensions?

There are several established methods when it comes to dimensionality reduction. The two major approaches are feature selection and feature extraction.

Feature extraction is where the data is mapped or transformed into a lower-dimensional space in a way that as much information is preserved about the original data as possible. There are a lot of methods that implement this approach, but the one I choose to describe in detail is Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in Section 4.2.2.

4.2.1 Feature selection

Feature selection is a method where the data is not transformed into a smaller dimensional space, only a subset of the existing attributes is selected. For example, irrelevant and redundant attributes are filtered. The three main feature selection

principles are filtering, wrapper, and embedded methods.

Filtering is part of pre-processing, and it is a fast and simple method with low resource requirements. It can be used independently of the subsequent learning algorithm. Attributes can be filtered, or in other words, excluded, based on various criteria such as missing value ratio, low variance, or high correlation with other features.

Wrapper methods evaluate variables according to how important they are to a specific algorithm. It takes a lot more processing power to run this method than filtering. The wrapper selects attributes that have good predictive power in a given model. We can choose from two strategies: forward and backward selection. With forward selection, the wrapper starts from the null model and takes in the attribute which reduces the squared error the most. With the backward selection, the wrapper starts from the model where every attribute is inside and drops out those that do not significantly reduce the model's performance.

Embedded methods are when the algorithm itself selects the variables during learning. It is an algorithm-specific procedure where the algorithms could be a decision tree or random forest, etc. The objective function has a regularization element that keeps the coefficient 0 for each attribute that is unimportant from the point of view of prediction. However, this does not solve the whole problem of the reduction, unfortunately.

4.2.2 Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [30] was invented in 1901 by Karl Pearson, but it was named by Harold Hotelling in the 1930s after he independently developed it [14]. PCA is also known as Hotelling transform, proper orthogonal decomposition (POD), etc. This method has a different name for every different field it is used in.

PCA is a popular feature extraction technique where a large data set with high-dimensional observations is mapped into a smaller dimensional space. For example, in Figure 4, PCA is used to visualize data points in two dimensions.

PCA linearly transforms the data into the needed number of dimensions while maintaining the transparency of all information. It eliminates the less important features and helps to visualize data, recognize clusters between data points, and helps in classifying data. It is widely used in Machine Learning. It has many applications in the fields of genetics, microbiology, etc., but it could also be applied in platforms like image identification, pattern identification, and so on.

Figure 4: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) illustration.

Source: http://www.nlpca.org/pca_principal_component_analysis.html

The goal of PCA is to find a projection that captures most of the variance in the data, in other words finding a maximum variance subspace. PCA searches for k vectors in a way that the squared projection error resulting from the projection onto the subspace spanned by these vectors is minimal. So the goal is to find the minimum of $\sum_{i=1}^m \|\underline{x}^{(i)} - \underline{x}_{approx}^{(i)}\|^2$ where m is the number of data points, $\underline{x}^{(i)}$ is the original data point and $\underline{x}_{approx}^{(i)}$ is the projected data point in the original space.

The new attributes will be the vectors (directions) that stretch out a subspace, such that projected data points carry as much information from the original data points as possible. These perpendicular vectors are called principal components that capture the directions with the largest variance in the data. The first principal component captures the largest, while the second one captures the largest that is perpendicular to the first direction, and so on. Thus, it can be shown that the i th principal component is the eigenvector that belongs to the i th largest eigenvalue in the covariance matrix, extracted from the data. By definition, the sample covariance matrix is a $n \times n$ symmetric matrix, where n denotes the number of dimensions. The entries are the sample covariances of the data points paired up in every possible way. For example, if $n = 3$ with variables x, y , and z , the covariance matrix is the following 3×3 matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Cov(x, x) & Cov(x, y) & Cov(x, z) \\ Cov(y, x) & Cov(y, y) & Cov(y, z) \\ Cov(z, x) & Cov(z, y) & Cov(z, z) \end{bmatrix}$$

Sample covariance between two attributes is calculated in the following way:

$$q_{jk} = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (x_{ij} - \underline{\mu}_j)(x_{ik} - \underline{\mu}_k)$$

where j and k denotes the two examined attributes from the attribute list, $\underline{\mu}$ is the

same as before and m is the number of records.

4.2.3 The steps of PCA

When working with PCA, one needs to take care that each initial column in the original data frame corresponds to a continuous or discrete variable, and they need to be put in the same range. In other words, we need to perform standardization. PCA is quite sensitive to variance. For example, if a given variable has large differences between their values, then it will dominate other variables with small ranges. This would lead to a biased result. Transforming the data to the same scale, by subtracting the mean and then dividing it by the standard deviation, can prevent this problem. With mathematical formulation, if we have m number of records and $\underline{x}^{(i)}$ is the i th indexed data point:

$$\frac{\underline{x}^{(i)} - \underline{\mu}}{\underline{\sigma}} \rightarrow \underline{x}^{(i)}$$

$$\text{where } \underline{\mu} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \underline{x}^{(i)} \text{ and } \underline{\sigma} = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (\underline{x}^{(i)} - \underline{\mu})^2$$

The following step is the computation of the sample covariance matrix. With this step, the algorithm explores the hidden connections between the variables to see if there is any relationship between them. It does this by looking at how the variables vary from the mean with respect to each other. If the correlation between variables is very high, then they carry redundant information, and one of them could be left out. The computation of the sample covariance matrix looks like the following, where m is the number of records and $\underline{x}^{(i)}$ is the i th indexed data point:

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (\underline{x}^{(i)})(\underline{x}^{(i)})^T$$

This step can be really slow but with a few tricks, it is achievable to reduce the number of calculations needed. For example, since it is a symmetric matrix it is only needed to calculate the upper or lower triangular matrix.

After this, the eigenvalues and the normalized eigenvectors of Σ are calculated. The sample covariance matrix is a positive semi-definite, which means all of its eigenvalues are greater or equal to zero. This means after calculating the values, it is possible to sort the eigenvalues in descending order as $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n \geq 0$. The normalized eigenvectors belonging to the eigenvalues are denoted as $\underline{u}^{(1)}, \underline{u}^{(2)} \dots \underline{u}^{(n)}$. From them, we are able to construct $U_{\text{reduce}} = (\underline{u}^{(1)} | \dots | \underline{u}^{(n)})$, which help us to deter-

mine the following values:

$$\underline{x}_{\text{approx}}^{(i)} = U_{\text{reduce}} \cdot U_{\text{reduce}}^T \cdot \underline{x}^{(i)}$$

An example of this mapping to a smaller dimensional space and transforming $\underline{x}^{(i)}$ to $\underline{x}_{\text{approx}}^{(i)}$ for $\forall i$ can be seen in Figure 4.

Sometimes the main goal of the PCA algorithm is not to visualize the data but rather to transform the data into being more manageable. This means that the number of components needed, k is dependent on the application. A good way to determine k is by choosing it in a way that the reconstruction error falls below a wanted threshold. The reconstruction error can be calculated by the following formulas:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \|\underline{x}^{(i)} - \underline{x}_{\text{approx}}^{(i)}\|^2}{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \|\underline{x}^{(i)}\|^2} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i}$$

The ratio of the sum of the first k eigenvalues to the sum of all eigenvalues is the proportion of the variance explained by the chosen principal components. We get the reconstruction error by subtracting this ratio value from 1.

In conclusion, PCA can be a long, computation-heavy process but fortunately, a great number of different implementations can be found in various programming languages, which greatly increase the efficiency of the method. PCA helps in preprocessing the data into the wanted number of dimensions, hence providing transparent data for further data analysis.

5 Ethereum dataset

5.1 Stablecoins

We have already discussed *dapps* in Section 2.2. Here, I introduce two *dapps*, *USDT*, and *USDC*, that I analyze in my experiments. These smart contracts are also available on several cryptocurrency networks such as Bitcoin [24], EOS [4], and Tron [34] but most importantly on Ethereum. *USDT* and *USDC* are both *stablecoins* that are by definition, designed to provide a stable price point at all times. These coins are fiat-collateralized *Stablecoins*, which means they are backed by a fiat currency. In this specific case, the currency is the American dollar (USD). Each token is worth one dollar and is backed by 1 USD in physical reserves. Since they are backed by the American dollar (USD), their volatility is identical to the dollar's, which is significantly less than Ethereum's in Figure 5. Hence the coins keep their valuation stable through the market, which is inviting for investors who want to keep value inside the crypto market but want to hedge against the inherent volatility of their cryptocurrency investments. Billions of these coins are exchanged every day. They are helping to bridge the gap between blockchain and fiat currencies.

Figure 5: ETH's, USD's, and gold's volatility compared
Source: <https://buybitcoinworldwide.com/volatility-index/>

USDT is also known as *Tether*. It was originally launched on the Bitcoin blockchain on October 6th, 2014, but now it can be issued on any chain that *Tether* supports, including the Ethereum network. It is the world's biggest *Stablecoin*. It uses a Proof Of Reserves method, which means that the amount of dollars in reserves is always at least the volume of Tether in circulation. It doesn't suffer from

market risks (such as Black Swan events) because of its large reserves. The value is entirely dependent on these large reserves, it will be worth 1 USD as long as each coin is backed by 1 USD. *Tether* has a circulating supply of around *83B* dollars that may increase or decrease according to the demand. Although it is backed by dollars, *Tether* cannot be exchanged directly for US dollars through the Tether company.

USDC is a digital dollar in the literal sense, it can be accessed whenever and wherever it is needed. *USDC* reserves are handled and preserved in the custody of top US financial organizations such as BlackRock and BNY Mellon. Anyone with internet access can use it and payments can circle the globe as fast as an email does. The coin is backed by the equivalent value of US dollars and its value is also dependent on the reserves, just like with *Tether*. Although its circulating supply is smaller, around *29.2B* dollars, it is considered safer to hold than *Tether*. *USDC* has a better reputation and more stability and also hasn't had issues with transparency and accountability.

5.2 Data collection

5.2.1 Banned users

USDT and *USDC* are accessible on the Ethereum network, they are decentralized smart contracts, but they have an owner. *USDC* is managed by a consortium called Centre, which was founded by Circle. *USDT* is managed by Tether Limited, and that company is owned by iFinex Inc. Smart contracts can have several functions that can be called by anyone or by only some people with special rights. For example, anyone can call the function which makes coin transfers between two accounts. On the other hand, there is a function called blacklist that bans addresses from using a given smart contract. This function can only be called by the contract owner.

```
1 SELECT COUNT(*)
2 FROM ethereum."logs" AS logs
3 WHERE logs."contract_address" = '\xdac17f958d2ee523a2206206994597c13d831ec7'
4 AND topic1= '\x42e160154868087d6bfdc0ca23d96a1c1cfa32f1b72ba9ba27b69b98a0d819dc'
```

Figure 6: An example of Dune's SQL query

The first step was to collect banned USDC and USDT addresses. For this task, I had to scan through all of the blocks committed to the blockchain. A dashboard on the Dune blockchain ecosystem analytics platform⁴ helped me in this process. In short, they provide an *SQL* code, such as in Figure 6, from which a *hexadecimal topic hash* can be extracted. This hash is different in the case of the two stablecoins

⁴USDC and USDT banned addresses: <https://dune.com/phabc/usdc-banned-addresses>, <https://dune.com/phabc/usdt---banned-addresses>

Figure 7: Banned addresses by dates

since they are smart contract specific. Doing an API search on all blocks with this topic gives back the desired content in JSON format, which can be transformed into a dataframe and after that it can be processed, shaped according to needs, and stored for later use.

Figure 7 shows the number of banned accounts by time. At the time of data collection in the March of 2023, 159 accounts were banned from *USDC* and 842 from *USDT*, including 6 addresses banned from both services. The bans are not uniformly distributed. There are larger waves of bans at both stablecoins related to different incidents. For example, on August 8th, 2022, the Ethereum smart-contract mixer Tornado Cash⁵ was sanctioned for money laundering, and several accounts were banned from using *USDC* because of it.

5.2.2 Collecting the neighborhood

For each banned address, I extracted its 2-radius neighborhood from the Ethereum transaction graph, where the nodes are addresses and the edges are transactions. More precisely, I used the Etherscan API⁶ to collect every address that is reachable within a two transactions radius from the given banned account. During data collection from Etherscan, I queried transaction data from all available channels, *txlist*,

⁵<https://github.com/tornadocash/docs>

⁶<https://docs.etherscan.io/>

	USDC	USDT	Sum
All channels	110	835	945
tokentx	80	834	914
txlist	102	593	695
txlistinternal	49	155	204

Table 1: Number of banned addresses with transactions on different channels for the two stablecoins USDC and USDT.

Channel	Edge weight	Node number	Edge number
tokentx	2.01335	31592.84902	36511.49562
txlist	4.72361	31359.66331	64859.64173
txlistinternal	3.83270	4552.89706	4709.58333

Table 2: Average network statistics for the extracted graphs around banned accounts for each channel.

tokentx, and *txlistinternal*, then I formed the related undirected networks that I classify in Chapter 6. Basically, you should think of channels as different transaction types. For example, *txlist* channel refers to all transactions initiated by a specific address except token transfers included in the *tokentx* channel. Finally, *txlistinternal* channel refers to all internal transfers, transactions received from smart contracts, related to the given address. Ethereum addresses not necessarily have transactions on all channels. For example, Table 1 shows, that only a subset of the analyzed banned nodes have internal transactions. It is also interesting to see that USDC addresses tend to have normal (*txlist*) transactions most of the time, but it is not true for the banned USDT accounts.

Finally, in Table 2, I describe some network statistics about the undirected graphs that I extracted around each banned address with a radius of two transactions. I chose to build undirected, connected, weighted graphs where the edge weight is the number of transactions that occurred between the given address pair. Additional information, like the transacted value, gas used, transaction fee, was excluded during my experiments. These graphs vastly differ in size, some of them have even hundreds of thousands of nodes. This makes the classification problem much more complex. However, with different techniques further analysis of the data, it was possible as can be seen in the upcoming chapter.

6 Experiments

All the experiments were conducted on my computer equipped with 8 CPU cores (Intel 9700k 3.6GHz processor) and 16GB RAM running Windows 10.

6.1 Graph classification

Graph classification is a complex problem. Given a set of graphs $\mathbb{G}$ and a set of labels Y corresponding to class labels, the task is to learn function $\mathcal{H} : \mathbb{G} \rightarrow Y$. A possible approach for graph classification is graph level embedding introduced in Chapter 3, where graphs are mapped to a low dimensional Euclidean space that preserves pairwise graph similarity in some context. Then, these representations are fed into downstream classifiers such as Random Forests, SVMs, and others used later in this section. Unfortunately, feeding graphs in the form of an adjacency matrix or edge list format is not a sufficient approach.

In my experiments, I rely on the *Karate Club* [32] Python library. *Karate Club* is an unsupervised machine learning library for NetworkX and it builds on several other processing packages. It provides embedding techniques at both node and graph level such as the aforementioned *Graph2Vec* (Section 3.3). With this algorithm, I generate three 128-dimensional embeddings for each address in our dataset, one for each channel (txlist, tokentx, txlistinternal). This means I handle the graph information from different channels independently when I train *Graph2Vec*. The embeddings were only trained once. All experiments presented later were performed on these embeddings. Due to the limited resources of my computer, I was unable to fit the model on all of the graphs at once. Thus, I split the graphs into four instances for training. Then, I perform binary classification for the label, whether the address in the center of a given graph was banned by *USDC* or *USDT*.

In Section 6.1.3, I present the results of an additional channel setup, where I concatenate the representations of the same address from the three original channels. If someone did not use a particular channel, those 128 numbers in the respective representation are filled with zeros. This way, every address has a 384-long vector, made up of the 3 different channels' 128-long vectors. The addresses that did not use any of the channels were dropped out. Also, addresses that were banned by both *USDT* and *USDC* were excluded from experiments. In the end, there are 945 addresses with embedded graphs.

6.1.1 Evaluation Metrics

In my experiments, I used various performance indicators. Firstly, let me introduce the confusion matrix, which is a matrix that summarizes the number of correct

		Predicted	
		Negative (N) -	Positive (P) +
Actual	Negative -	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP) Type I Error
	Positive +	False Negative (FN) Type II Error	True Positive (TP)

Figure 8: The confusion matrix

Source: <https://medium.com/analytics-vidhya/what-is-a-confusion-matrix-d1c0f8feda5>

and incorrect predictions. Its entries represent the number of true negative (TN), false positive (FP), false negative (FN) and true positive (TP) predictions as shown in Figure 8. In Table 4, the two classes in my experiments are 0 (*Negative*) and 1 (*Positive*), where 0 corresponds to the **USDT** class and 1 corresponds to the **USDC** class.

Furthermore, I also evaluated the performance of the classification models for various performance metrics. Namely the followings:

$$Accuracy : A = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}, \quad Precision : P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$Recall (sensitivity, TPR) : R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \quad F-score : F = \frac{2 \cdot TP}{2 \cdot TP + FP + FN}$$

Although these metrics are able to determine the performance of the models, there is an even better performance measure. The ROC (*Receiver Operating Characteristics*) curve is a graph showing the performance of the given binary classification model at various decision thresholds. A Machine Learning model with a binary classification problem gives a probability for each element in the dataset that measures how likely it is that the element belongs to class 1. After this, the elements get sorted in ascending order by these probabilities, and every point above the wanted threshold will be labeled as class 1, and others will be labeled class 0. At every threshold, we measure TPR (*Recall*) and $FPR = \frac{FP}{FP+TN}$. The representation of TPR as a function of FPR is the ROC curve. The area under this curve, the ROC AUC score, is used to measure model performance in a single metric. Its value ranges from 0 to 1, 0 being the model whose predictions are all wrong and 1 being the model whose predictions are all correct.

6.1.2 Classification models

In my experiments, I used five different classifiers from the *Scikit-Learn*⁷ Python library on the representations learned by whole graph embedding. In the following few paragraphs, I will briefly introduce these models.

To introduce *Random Forests* [5], we need to define *decision trees* [6]. The name comes from the fact that tree alike branches are built in a hierarchical structure, where each branch is a decision that can be considered an if-else statement. Branches are formed by dividing the dataset into smaller subsets based on the most important features. Classification happens at the leaves of the tree. As the name suggests, these trees make up *Random Forest*. It is an ensemble method [10], which combines the results from multiple weak classifiers. Each tree in the forest is trained on a random sample of the original dataset to avoid overfitting. This technique is called bagging. The final prediction is the majority vote from all trees, which leads to Random Forests having better generalization.

Adaptive Boosting [12] also known as *AdaBoost* is another ensemble model. In my experiments, it combines the prediction of multiple decision trees with a maximum depth of one, basically a single decision in each tree. It first fits a classifier on the original dataset, then fits additional copies of the classifier on weighted samples of the same dataset, where high weight is assigned to data instances misclassified by previous trees. This way the model concentrates more on challenging cases. The final decision is based on the weighted majority vote of all trees, where tree weights are in relation to their performance.

Logistic regression [9] uses the sigmoid function, which maps any real value to a value between 0 and 1, to generate probability outputs of labels for binary classification tasks. By comparing these probabilities to a predefined threshold, the algorithm predicts the label for each element in the dataset. It is a computationally efficient algorithm, so it can be used on large and high-dimensional datasets. However, it assumes that the variables have a linear relationship. If that is not the case, then

Figure 9: The ROC curve

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Receiver_operating_characteristic

⁷<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

the model is not the most suitable.

Support Vector Machines [7] or *SVM* for short is another machine learning algorithm used for both classification and regression tasks. SVC (support vector classifier) is for classification problems. It finds the best way to classify the data by finding an optimal hyperplane that not only separates the different classes but also maximizes the distance from the nearest data points of each class and minimizes the classification error. The key strength of this classifier is its ability to handle both linearly separable and linearly inseparable data by using different kernel functions. With these functions, the original feature space can be transformed into a higher-dimensional space, where the linearly inseparable data might become linearly separable. This way, SVC can effectively find complex decision boundaries. It is also robust to overfitting and good in generalizing.

Finally, *k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN)* [8] is an instance-based algorithm used for classification and regression tasks. It is a very simple yet effective method that utilizes the similarities between the data points in the feature space. In a binary classification problem, the predictions are determined by the labels of the k nearest neighbors, respectively, to the data points. The neighbors are determined based on a distance metric. Its performance heavily relies on the k parameter, where a choice of low k leads to increased sensitivity to noise, and a high k leads to smoothing the decision boundary.

6.1.3 Results

As discussed in Section 5.2.2, we use data from multiple transaction channels. The number of addresses used in my experiments is shown in Table 1.

Firstly, every channel setup was evaluated on different train/test split ratios with default classifier parameters to see how they perform in the binary classification task, described in Section 6.1. In Figures 10 12 14 16 and 18, the x-axis shows the train/test split ratio, while the y-axis is the model’s ROC AUC score on the corresponding test set. Since our task is strongly related to USDC and USDT token transfers, we expected that the best-performing channel setup would be *tokentx* or the aggregated *all channels* setup, that contains the embeddings of the *tokentx* graphs as well. The results show that our expectation was correct. Looking at the figures also tells us that, for most classifiers, larger training data means better performance.

Next, we fix the train/test split to be 0.6/0.4, which means 60% train and 40% test data. To achieve more accurate results for this setup, I tune model parameters with 5-fold cross-validation. Cross-validation is a technique for evaluating Machine Learning models by training several models on subsets of the available input data and evaluating them on the complementary subset of the data. This method helps

to avoid overfitting. For the parameter tuning I used *Scikit Learn*'s built-in Grid-SearchCV⁸ method, as shown in Figures 11 13 15 17 and 19. The figures only show the results of the grid search for the *all channels* setup but the tuning was completed on all channel setups.

With the optimal parameter settings, I evaluated all classifiers for all of the channel setups with various performance metrics in Table 3. The accuracy is really high for all classifiers, while precision, recall, and F1 scores vary over the rows. This might be due to the *USDT* class's dominance in size over *USDC*. According to Table 4, the models are performing well in terms of overall correct predictions that is why the accuracy score is high. Overall the mean of the precision scores is also high, that is because all the classifiers correctly identify class 1 instances and do not mislabel class 0 instances as class 1, resulting in very low *False Positive* predictions as can be seen on the top right of the confusion matrices in Table 4. However, looking at the lower left numbers, we see that if classifiers make bad predictions they are usually *False Negative* mistakes. This explains why the *recall* scores have a huge variance among the rows of Table 3 and why these scores are usually lower than the *precision* scores. The F1-score shows how good the balance is between precision and recall among the classifiers and since these values vary, the F1-scores also vary from low to high values as expected.

Finally, I note that the *random state = 21* was globally fixed for each and every experiment in order to get reproducible results. Threshold values corresponding to performance metrics were all set to the default value.

⁸https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.model_selection.GridSearchCV.html

	Channel	ROC AUC	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Random Forest	All channels	0.829787	0.957672	1.000000	0.659574	0.794872
	tokentx	0.838915	0.957672	0.969697	0.680851	0.800000
	txlist	0.723404	0.931217	1.000000	0.446809	0.617647
	txlistinternal	0.636787	0.907407	0.928571	0.276596	0.426230
Logistic Regression	All channels	0.811596	0.941799	0.857143	0.638298	0.731707
	tokentx	0.577682	0.851852	0.344828	0.212766	0.263158
	txlist	0.661149	0.902116	0.727273	0.340426	0.463768
	txlistinternal	0.595745	0.899471	1.000000	0.191489	0.321429
Non-linear SVM	All channels	0.943787	0.981481	0.954545	0.893617	0.923077
	tokentx	0.886064	0.960317	0.880952	0.787234	0.831461
	txlist	0.772064	0.936508	0.896552	0.553191	0.684211
	txlistinternal	0.531915	0.883598	1.000000	0.063830	0.120000
AdaBoost	All channels	0.869319	0.962963	0.945946	0.744681	0.833333
	tokentx	0.802468	0.941799	0.878788	0.617021	0.725000
	txlist	0.679340	0.917989	0.944444	0.361702	0.523077
	txlistinternal	0.557787	0.880952	0.600000	0.127660	0.210526
kNN	All channels	0.734043	0.933862	1.000000	0.468085	0.637681
	tokentx	0.849553	0.960317	0.970588	0.702128	0.814815
	txlist	0.720383	0.925926	0.913043	0.446809	0.600000
	txlistinternal	0.617021	0.904762	1.000000	0.234043	0.379310

Table 3: Evaluation on different channels with fine-tuned parameters on 0.6/0.4 train/test split.

	Predicted 0	Predicted 1		Predicted 0	Predicted 1	
True 0	326	5	True 0	331	0	
True 1	18	29	True 1	16	31	
(a) Logistic Regression			(b) Random Forest			
	Pred 0	Pred 1	Pred 0	Pred 1	Pred 0	Pred 1
True 0	329	2	329	2	331	0
True 1	5	42	12	35	25	22
(c) SVM			(d) AdaBoost		(e) kNN	

Table 4: Confusion matrix for the *all channels* setup with fine-tuned parameters. The USDT and USDC classes are marked by 0 and 1, respectively.

Figure 10: Random Forest ROC AUC scores for multiple channel setting.

Figure 11: Random Forest parameter tuning with grid search on *all channels* setup.

Figure 12: Logistic Regression ROC AUC scores for multiple channel setting.

Figure 13: Logistic Regression parameter tuning with grid search on *all channels* setup.

Figure 14: Non-linear SVM ROC AUC scores for multiple channel setting.

Figure 15: Non-linear SVM parameter tuning with grid search on *all channels* setup.

Figure 16: AdaBoost ROC AUC scores for multiple channel setting.

Figure 17: AdaBoost parameter tuning with grid search on *all channels* setup.

Figure 18: kNN ROC AUC scores for multiple channel setting.

Figure 19: kNN parameter tuning with grid search on *all channels* setup.

6.2 Embedding visualization

In my experiments, I obtained high classification accuracy for all channels, especially considering that I collected all the transactions in connection with the addresses, not just the *tokentx* ones where the use of the stablecoins is present. This leads me to the conclusion that the two classes are non-linearly separable in the *Graph2Vec* embedding space. To confirm this conclusion I used *PCA*, introduced in Section 4.2.2, to visualize the 384-dimensional concatenated *Graph2Vec* embeddings in two di-

mensions. Even for two principal components, in Figure 20, we can see clusters of addresses blocked by *USDT* and *USDC*, respectively. In the original embedding space, addresses are even more separated as the two principal components only attend to 46.45% and 8.18% of the variance of the embedded data points.

Figure 20: Concatenated *Graph2Vec* vectors of the *all channels* setup mapped to two dimensions with PCA. The two axis represents the two principal components.

In the following, I would like to demonstrate that whole graph embedding can capture various global graph properties extremely well, such as the number of edges, number of nodes, edge density, average node degree, and assortativity. In Figures 21–27, these properties are all presented on a base 10 logarithmic scale, except assortativity where there are negative numbers.

Since the graph-building process 5.2 was made separately for different channels, there are no aggregated graphs containing all channels transactions for the banned accounts, but the representation can be made for the three different channels. For the sake of clarity, in Figures 21–25, I only present the distribution of the *txlistinternal* graphs by these properties in the *Graph2Vec* embedding space.

Figure 21: Txlistinternal graphs number of nodes distribution after PCA.

Figure 22: Txlistinternal graphs number of edges distribution after PCA.

Figure 23: Txlistinternal graphs density distribution after PCA.

Figure 24: Txlistinternal graphs average degree distribution after PCA.

Figure 25: Txlistinternal graphs assortativity distribution after PCA.

As it can be seen in Figures 21 and 22, the distribution of the number of nodes and edges are highly correlated as expected. From the other figures, it can be seen that larger graphs with more nodes and edges tend to have a lower density, average degree, and assortativity. This makes sense since smaller networks have a lower maximum number of edges than the bigger networks and nodes are more likely to be connected to each other in smaller networks.

Results for the *txlist* and *tokenrx* channels can be seen in the Appendix 7.

7 Summary

In this thesis, first I introduced the fundamental concepts of blockchain technology, with a specific emphasis on Ethereum and its key features. Next, I showed the significance and employment of graph-level embeddings, aiming to capture the structural and semantic information of the Ethereum network in a low-dimensional vector space. Additionally, dimensionality reduction methods were introduced and employed to highlight certain properties of the collected data.

As an important achievement, I created a data collection for this thesis from the Ethereum blockchain. I used Etherscan to query all addresses within a two-transaction radius around accounts banned by the USDC or USDT smart contracts. The graph classification task that I solved in this thesis is to decide whether a given graph belongs to an address that was banned by USDC or USDT. First, I mapped each transaction graph to a low-dimensional vector space with *Graph2Vec* [25]. Then, I applied various downstream classifiers to solve this binary classification problem.

Through my experiments, I evaluated the performance of five different classification models using various performance indicators. I demonstrated the effectiveness of the *Graph2Vec* data-driven representation learning method of whole graphs and the separability of the two graph classes (USDC or USDT banned) in the embedding space. While all classifiers accomplished good results in general, some struggled to differentiate USDC-banned addresses from USDT-banned ones, while USDT-related graphs were rarely mislabeled. This observation is supported by the high number of *False Negative* and the low number of *False Positive* cases. Nonetheless, a fine-tuned *Support Vector Classifier (SVC)* performed exceptionally well in my measurements.

Additionally, I showcased the separability of the two graph classes in the *Graph2Vec* embedding space using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Furthermore, I also visualize the global graph properties captured by *Graph2Vec* along the principal components.

In conclusion, the findings of this thesis demonstrate the potential for analyzing blockchain networks using graph embedding. To further enhance the performance, I suggest exploring algorithms for balancing the class sizes, as well as investigating the applicability of further graph embedding techniques. These experiments did not fit into the scope of this thesis.

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Appendix

Figure 26: Tokentx graphs embedding space after PCA.

Figure 27: Txlist graphs embedding space after PCA.